

Photocatalytic degradation of Acridine Yellow G and Aniline Blue B dyes in a slurry batch reactor using visible light and ZnO suspension

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Abstract : The photocatalysed degradation of two selected dyes, such as Acridine Yellow G (AYG) and Aniline Blue B (ABB) was investigated in aqueous suspensions of ZnO under visible irradiation. The degradation of selected dyes was studied using different parameters such as, reaction pH, catalyst concentration, substrate concentration and in the presence of different electron acceptors such as hydrogen peroxide, potassium persulphate. The degradation was strongly influenced by all the above-mentioned parameters. Visible light and ZnO system was found to degrade AYG more efficiently as compared to ABB under chosen reaction conditions.

Keywords : Photocatalytic degradation, visible light, ZnO, Acridine Yellow G, Aniline Blue B.

Introduction

Among the different physical components, water is the most essential component of life. Total amount of water existing in the earth in the form of ground water, surface water, etc. is 1.4×10^9 km³ approximately¹. Addition of artificial foreign matter from various sources such as industrial effluents, agricultural runoff and chemical spills contaminates the water². These effluents include several non-biodegradable, toxic organic substances like pesticides, herbicides, dyes, etc. These substances are highly toxic, stable to natural decomposition and are persistent to the environment. Of all these organic substances, dyes pose a great threat to the environment³. Recent studies indicate that during manufacturing and processing operations substantial amount of dyestuff is lost and resultant color enters the environment through effluents from industrial wastewater treatment plants⁴. Decomposition of dye effluents has therefore acquired increasing attention. Recently there has been considerable interest in the utilization of advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) for the complete destruction of dyes.

AOPs are based on generation of reactive species such as hydroxyl radicals that oxidizes a broad range of organic pollutants quickly and non-selectively⁵.

Heterogeneous photocatalysis on semiconductor surfaces has attracted a lot of attention due to important applications like water disinfection, degradation and complete mineralization of organic contaminants in wastewater⁶.

During the past two decades, photocatalytic degradation involving semiconductor particles under UV-light illumination has become a promising technology for the removal of toxic organic and inorganic contaminants from wastewater.

Many photocatalyst like TiO₂, ZnO, ZrO₂, WO₃, SrO₂, Fe₂O₃, CeO₂, CdS and ZnS have been attempted for the photocatalytic degradation of a wide variety of environmental contaminants^{7,9}. Out of these, ZnO and TiO₂ are prominent. Recently, TiO₂ and ZnO are used as effective and nontoxic semiconductor photocatalysts for the degradation of wide range of organic chemicals and synthetic dyes^{10,14}. TiO₂ is mainly UV-light active photocatalyst. However wide spread use of TiO₂ is uneconomic for the large-scale water operations because solar UV-light reaching surface of the earth and available to excite TiO₂ is relatively small and artificial UV-light source are somewhat expensive¹⁵. Among others, zinc oxide appears as a very promising photocatalyst for degradation of organic

Fig. 1. Photocatalytic degradation of dyes on the surface of the photocatalyst.

solutes in aqueous systems. In some cases, zinc oxide was more effective than TiO_2 . Thus, ZnO appears to be a suitable alternative to TiO_2 . Acridine Yellow G (AYG) and Aniline Blue B (ABB) dyes are extensively used in textile industry, leather dyeing, paper printing, photography and as a biological stain^{16,17}, therefore, we have undertaken, photodegradation of the AYG and ABB sensitized by ZnO under visible solution.

Fig. 2. Structure of Acridine Yellow G.

Experimental

AYG and ABB dyes were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Company (India). The photocatalyst ZnO was obtained from Merck Company (New Delhi, India), about 99% pure with surface area of $10 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. H_2O_2 (30% aqueous), FeCl_3 , FeSO_4 , NaCl and Na_2CO_3 were of analytical grade and used without further purification. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The photocatalytic and photolytic experiments were carried out in a slurry type batch reactor having pyrex vessel of dimension of $7.5 \text{ cm} \times 6 \text{ cm}$ (height \times dia.). The pyrex glass vessel equipped with magnetic stirrer was surrounded by thermostatic water circulation arrangement to keep temperature in the range of $30 \pm 0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The irradiation was carried out using 500 W halogen lamps (Philips,

Fig. 3. Structure of Aniline Blue B.

India) surrounded with aluminium reflectors in order to avoid loss of irradiation¹⁸. During the photocatalytic experiment, after stirring for ten minute, the slurry composed of dye solution and catalyst was placed in dark for half an hour in the order to establish equilibrium between adsorption and desorption phenomenon of dye molecule on the surface of photocatalyst. Now slurry containing aqueous dye solution and ZnO particles was stirred magnetically to ensure complete suspension of catalyst particle with simultaneous exposure to visible light. At specific time intervals, aliquot (3 mL) was withdrawn and centrifuged for 2 min at the rate of 3500 rpm. The changes in absorption spectra were recorded at λ_{max} on double-beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1700). pH was constantly monitored and not adjusted unless otherwise stated. The COD and CO_2 ion estimation were performed by methods reported in literature^{19,20}. The efficiency of photocatalytic process was investigated by us-

ing following formula,

$$\% \text{ Efficiency} = C_0 - C/C_0 \times 100$$

where C_0 is the initial COD/absorbance and C in the COD/absorbance in different time interval for photocatalytic process.

(1) Double wall cylinder, (2) Magnetic stirrer, (3) Thermostatic bath, (4) Water circulation arrangement, (5) Halogen lamp (500 W), (6) Aluminium reflector, (7) pH meter, (8) Thermometer, (9) Teflon coated magnetic capsule, (10) Dye solution containing ZnO.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of photoreactors.

Results and discussion

Irradiation of aqueous suspension of AYG and ABB in the presence of ZnO with a halogen lamp led to change in absorption intensity as a function of irradiation time. Fig. 5 shows the change in absorbance as a function of time on irradiation of an aqueous solution of AYG and ABB both in the presence and in the absence of the photocatalyst. 88% and 75% degradation was observed for AYG and ABB respectively in 2 h of irradiation, whereas in the absence of photocatalyst, no observable loss of the dye could be seen.

Fig. 5 was fitted reasonably well by exponential decay curve suggesting the first order kinetics. For each experiment, the degradation rate constant of the dye was calculated from the plot of the natural logarithm of the

Fig. 5. Photodecolorisation of AYG and ABB under ZnO/visible system. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} ; ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} ; amount of ZnO : 200 mg/100 ml; irradiation intensity = 27×10^3 lux, pH = 7.1.

concentration of the dye as a function of irradiation time.

At $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 440$ nm (AYG) : Rate constant,

$$k = 6.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}, R^2 = 0.97$$

At $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 580$ nm (ABB) : Rate constant,

$$k = 2.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}, R^2 = 0.98$$

Effect of catalyst loading :

The effect of catalyst loading on selected dye is given in Fig. 6. The rate of degradation of both the dyes increased with the increase in catalyst concentration from 50 mg/100 ml to 200 mg/100 ml and further increase in catalyst concentration resulted in decrease in rate con-

Fig. 6. Effect of catalyst loading. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} ; ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} ; irradiation intensity : 27×10^3 lux; pH = 7.1.

stant of photocatalytic reaction. This observation indicates that beyond this optimum catalyst concentration, other factors affect the degradation of dyes. At high ZnO concentrations, particles aggregate which in turn reduces the interfacial area between the reaction solution and the photocatalyst. Thus, the number of active sites on the catalyst surface is decreased. The increase in opacity and light scattering by the particle may be the other reasons for the decrease in the degradation rate at higher catalyst concentration^{21,18}.

Effect of substrate concentration :

Effect of substrate concentration on the degradation of the AYG and ABB was studied at different concentrations varying from 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ to 6.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 7). The rate constant (k) for the degradation of AYG decreased with the increase in substrate concentration and highest efficiency was obtained at 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. On the other hand, in the case of ABB, the rate constant increased with the increase in substrate concentration from 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ to 3.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. The rate constant decreased with further increase in ABB concentration. As the dye concentration increases, the color of the irradiating mixture becomes more and more intense which prevents the penetration of light to the surface of the catalyst. Hence, the generation of relative amount of OH⁻ and O²⁻ on the surface of the catalyst do not increase as the intensity of light, irradiation time and catalyst concentration are constant. Con-

Fig. 7. Effect of initial dye concentration. Amount of ZnO : 200 mg/100 ml; irradiation intensity : 27×10^3 lux; pH = 7.1.

versely, their concentrations will decrease with increase in concentration of the dye as the light photons are largely absorbed and prevented from reaching the catalyst surface by the dye molecules. Consequently, in case of ABB above optimal concentration, rate constant decreased with an increase in dye concentration^{22,21,18}.

Effect of electron acceptors :

The effect of electron acceptors such as hydrogen peroxide, and persulphate ions on the photocatalytic degradation of AYG and ABB was studied and results are given in Fig. 8. The rate constant increased from 6.3×10^{-4} s⁻¹ to 11.0×10^{-4} s⁻¹ with increase in H₂O₂ concentration from 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ to 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ in case of AYG. Further increase in H₂O₂ concentration

Fig. 8. Effect of oxidant. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; amount of ZnO : 200 mg/100 ml; irradiation intensity : 27×10^3 lux ; pH = 7.1.

resulted in decrease in degradation rate. Similar trend was observed for the degradation of ABB with optimal concentration of 3.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ (H₂O₂). The increase in degradation rate of AYG and ABB on the addition of H₂O₂ can be rationalized in terms of several reasons. The added hydrogen peroxide could inhibit the electron hole recombination by accepting photogenerated electron from the conduction band of semiconductor and promotes charge separation and it forms hydroxyl radical. By addition of excess H₂O₂, it acts as hydroxyl radical or hole scavenger to form the perhydroxyl radical (HO₂[•]), which is much weaker oxidant than hydroxyl radicals²³.

From Fig. 8, the degradation rate of AYG and ABB were found to be maximal at 3.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ of K₂S₂O₈. K₂S₂O₈ can also trap the photogenerated conduction band electron to produce sulphate ion with (standard reduction potential = 2.6 eV). Photocatalytic process has been accelerated according to eqs. (4)–(6). The decrease in rate of photodegradation above optimal concentration (3.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³), was due to the adsorption of sulphate ions on surface of ZnO formed during the reaction^{21–23}.

Effect of hydroxyl radical acceptors :

The photocatalysis involves bulk degradation of dye molecule by hydroxyl radicals on the surface of photocatalyst. In the order to evaluate this path, experimental studies were performed by the addition of different concentration of anionic species, such as, NaCl and Na₂CO₃ to the reaction solution. The effect of presence of NaCl and Na₂CO₃ is presented in Fig. 9. An increment in concentration of Cl⁻ and CO₃²⁻ from 3.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ to 11.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ resulted in reduction of rate constant for AYG and ABB. The inhibition is undoubtedly due to their ability to act as hydroxyl radical (OH[•])

Fig. 9. Effect of salt concentration. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; amount of ZnO : 200 mg/100 ml; irradiation intensity : 27×10^3 lux; pH = 7.1.

scavengers. The observed mechanism of hydroxyl radical scavenging is given by eqs. (7)–(10)^{20,21,23}.

From this experimental study, it can be concluded that hydroxyl radicals play a major role in photocatalytic degradation process. Behnajady *et al.* reported the similar studies about photocatalytic degradation of C. I. Yellow 23²⁴.

Effect of pH :

The wastewater from textile industries usually has a wide range of pH values. Further, the generation of hydroxyl radicals is also a function of pH. Thus, pH plays an important role both in the characteristics of textile wastes and generation of hydroxyl radicals. Photodegradation process was examined at pH values ranging from 4 to 10 for both AYG and ABB dyes. The effect of pH on the degradation is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Effect of pH. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; amount of ZnO 200 mg/100 ml; irradiation intensity : 27×10^3 lux.

In case of AYG dye, the rate constant increased from 4.0×10^{-4} s⁻¹ to 9.8×10^{-4} s⁻¹ with change in reaction pH 4 to 8. Further increase in pH caused a reduction in value of rate constant. Similar trend was obtained for ABB dye. Highest efficiency for dye degradation was observed between at pH 7–8 for both AYG and ABB. The pH of zero point charge for ZnO is about 9²⁵. At pH

value, 7–8 due to metal-bound OH⁻, negatively charged active sites on the surface of catalyst are preferentially covered by positively charged dye molecule. At lower value of pH, ~4, positively charged active sites on the surface of catalyst, results in low concentration of positively charged of dye molecule on the surface of catalyst. At higher pH, surface concentration of dye molecules and hydroxyl radicals increases. But ZnO is amphoteric in nature. It gets dissolved at lower pH, forming salts. At higher pH, it forms zincates such as [Zn(OH)₄]²⁻. All these factors are responsible for optimum value of photodegradation of selected dyes at pH 7–8. Our results are in agreement with other studies^{17,20,21,13}.

Effect of other photocatalysts :

Experiments were performed with other photocatalysts as well. The order of photoactivity followed the order : ZnO > TiO₂ > CdS for AYG and ABB. Generally, semiconductors having large band gaps are good photocatalysts. It has already been reported that semiconductors such as ZnO and TiO₂ have band gaps larger than 3 eV show strong photocatalytic activity. The conduction and valence band potentials of both ZnO and TiO₂ are larger than the corresponding redox potentials of H⁺/H₂ and H₂O/O₂ and the photogenerated electron and hole can be separated efficiently. CdS with smaller band gap shows less activity since its conduction band is much lower than that of ZnO and TiO₂. Electron (CB) in these semiconductors rapidly falls into the hole thus showing reduced activity.

Effect of solar light :

Use of solar light in place of artificial irradiation is preferred from the industrial point of view. Aqueous solu-

Fig. 11. Effect of solar light. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; amount of ZnO : 200 mg/100 ml; irradiation intensity : 40×10^3 lux; pH = 7.1.

tions of AYG and ABB were exposed to sunlight in the presence of ZnO (Fig. 11). It was found that the degradation of selected dye proceeded much more rapidly in the presence of solar light (intensity = $185 \times 10^3 \pm 5$ lux). Blank experiments were carried out under sunlight in absence of ZnO where no observable loss of dye was observed.

COD and CO₂ analysis during degradation of AYG and ABB :

COD values are related to the total concentration of organics in the solutions. Using this criterion, the mineralization of ABB and AYG was investigated under ZnO/Vis process. COD and CO₂ measurements were carried out. From measured COD values, the COD removal efficiency values were calculated (Table 1). The reduction in the estimated COD value from 100 mg/L to 0 mg/L and

Table 1. COD and CO₂ measurements for degradation of AYG and ABB. AYG concentration : 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻¹; ABB concentration : 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻¹; amount of ZnO : 200 mg/100 ml

Irradiation time (h)	Acridine Yellow G (AYG)					Aniline Blue B (ABB)				
	COD (mg/L)	CO ₂ (mg/L)	% Efficiency	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	COD (mg/L)	CO ₂ (mg/L)	% Efficiency	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)
0	100	10	0	6.12	0.754	1760	20	0	6	0.65
1	56	12	16	6	0.8	1736	22	1.2	5.9	0.654
2	40	15	46	5.9	0.854	1720	22	2.2	5.85	0.660
3	20	20	60	5.8	0.89	896	33	49	5.84	0.67
4	10	22	80	5.7	0.912	760	33	59	5.8	0.68
5	0	23	100	5.5	0.920	750	40	63	5.79	0.71

increase in 10 mg/L value from 23 mg/L in 10 h of illumination indicated the photodegradation AYG dye solution. A decrease in pH and increase in conductivity of solution was observed with increase in the extent of degradation. In case of ABB, the COD removal efficiency was found to be 63% for the process in 5 h of irradiation time. CO₂ increased from 20 mg/L to 40 mg/L during the degradation of ABB.

Mechanism :

When illuminated with visible radiation, the photocatalyst generates electron/hole pairs with free electrons produced in the nearby free conduction band leaving positive holes in valence band as shown in Fig. 1. The holes at ZnO valence band can oxidize adsorbed water molecules or hydroxide radicals to produce hydroxyl radicals, a very strong oxidizing agent^{25,12,14}.

In second way, dye molecules act as a sensitizer by the absorption of visible light, and the transfer of photogenerated electrons from the dye molecule to semiconductor has been reported to be very effective^{13,24}.

Degradation of Dye involving organic intermediates

Mineralization

Conclusions :

The detailed investigation revealed that under chosen experimental condition AYG was completely mineralized while ABB got mineralized only 63%. In the presence of

ZnO and visible light, K₂S₂O₈ and FeCl₃ had maximal effect on degradation of ABB and AYG. Fe³⁺/H₂O₂/ZnO process decolorizes the selected dye effectively. The degradation condition varied with the nature of the dye. The proposed green method of dye removal has been found to be safe and efficient.

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